

Influence of Manufacturing process based Microstructural Variations on the Damage Behaviour of Braided Composites

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Northwest Composites Centre

A little bit about the facility in Manchester

- The Henry Moseley X-ray Imaging Facility is part of the NXCT
- We house ~11 X-ray CT systems including high resolution cabinet systems, walk-in bays and custom research set-ups
- We have a large number of in-situ rigs we use both in-house and send to various beamlines in the UK and abroad

Nikon XTH 225

Versa 520 & 620 (2 systems!)

Zeiss ultra

320/225kV

Spectroscopic imaging bay

Sigray Prisma

High flux bay

FEI HeliScan

2-25 kN Deben Rig

Compressive and tensile operation modes capable of imaging over 360 degrees

3 kN Bose-Deben Fatigue Rig

Purpose built X-ray CT tension-compression in-situ fatigue rig with waveform, amplitude and phase compensation functions

10 kN Open Frame Deben Rig

Sample can be rotated through 360 degrees whilst maintaining tensile/compression and torsion effects

5 kN Deben Rig

A modular tensile and compression testing system

Microtesting Rig

Specifically designed for in-situ micro-mechanical compression/tension experiments on XCT and SEM

Zeiss Ultra In-situ Load Cell

Mechanical loading (compression, tension and indentation) on the ZEISS Xradia 810 Ultra

Dual Phase Flow DTU Rig

Designed and built to conduct reactive percolation on geologic materials with tuneable solution chemistry

650 degree Celsius MRI Furnace

Temperature range from room temperature to 650 degree celsius and capable of imaging specimens over 360 degrees

Braiding

is the formation of comparatively narrow fabrics or rope-like structures by diagonally interlacing three or more strands of material.

From Manchester textile composite group

- ✓ Automated process
- ✓ Low costs for large quantity manufacturing
- ✓ High flexibility for complex-shaped structures
- Limited component size

Application of braiding tubes

Damage of braided composite driving shaft

Infusion Process

Vacuum Infusion (VI)

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM)

Aim and Objectives

Objectives

- Link1: Identify the **braided structure differences** between different manufacturing process
- Link2: Identify **damage evolution**/sequence of events during torsional failure
- Link3: **Optimise** the manufacturing process of braided structures
- **Final goals:** Build safer, more economical and faster braided structure design strategy

Geometry comparison – X-ray CT slices

Geometry comparison

- +45° tow (tension tow)
- -45° tow (compression tow)

3D visualization of braided structures

S1-1/1-45° Strain – Stress

	VI	RTM
Fibre volume fraction	55%	34%
Crimp angle	32.3°	21.8°
Shear modulus	8.1 Gpa	5.8 Gpa
Shear stiffness	393 N*m/rad	645 N*m/rad

Time-lapse X-ray Computed Tomography (CT)

(a)

(b)

(a) Lab based X-rays**(b) Synchrotron X-rays**Resolutions from 100 μm
to 50 nmResolutions from 20 μm to
30 nmAcquisitions from minutes
to many hoursHigh flux, high brightness
enabling up to 20
tomograms per secondFew machines capable of
phase contrastExcellent phase contrast,
no beam hardening, high
signal to noiseDifficult to accommodate
the rigAppropriate for in situ
experiments

In-situ X-ray Imaging (synchrotron)

Benefits compared with traditional characterisation techniques

- ✓ 3D imaging
- ✓ Can follow evolution over time, load, during degradation

- I13-2 beamline, Diamond Light Source
- Voxel size 2.25 μm

Damage 3D volume rendering (RTM)

3D volume rendering (Intra_tow cracking) - VI

B: $\gamma = 0.5\%$

1 mm

- +45° tow
- -45° tow
- Intra_tow cracking

C: $\gamma = 0.75\%$

D: $\gamma = 1.5\%$

G: $\gamma = 3\%$

J: $\gamma = 6\%$

K: $\gamma = 8\%$

3D volume rendering (Inter_tow debonding) - VI

Inter_tow debonding area projection

VI

RTM

Qualitative analysis

VI

RTM

1 mm

VI

A 0% E 1.5% F 2% G 3% H 4% J 6% K 8%

Increasing shear strain →

RTM

- A: Debonding*
- B: crack (transverse tension)*
- D: crack (transverse compression)*
- E: Micro kinking*

Damage sequence

Kink band formation

VI

G
3%

RTM

VI

H
4%

RTM

VI

J
6%

RTM

K
8%

Conclusion and future work

- VI reduce the **curvature** of the inner diameter fibre tow. It make the flat surface more sensitive to cracking (damage initiation).
- VI mitigate **resin-rich areas** (providing higher fibre volume fraction), resulting in a higher shear modulus of the sample.
- The **crimp angle** may also increase due to the vacuum pressure acting on the fibre surface, which in turn leads to a reduction in the strength of the sample.
- VI provided **stronger interface**, suppressing the occurrence of interfacial debonding. VI sample is dominant by cracking (traverse compression), but RTM sample (debonding).
- Both VI and RTM sample reach the shear strength around **2.5 %** strain, with the formation of **kink band**.

Future work

- Imaged based modelling combining with DVC

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DEBEN

Thank you!

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HENRY
ROYCE
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